

Geographical Review of India

VOLUME: 58

JUNE: 1996

NUMBER: 2

Location of the Adi Ganga Palaeochannel, South 24-Parganas, West Bengal : A Review

Sunando Bandyopadhyay

Department of Geography & Environment Management, Vidyasagar University,
Medinipur-721102, West Bengal.

ABSTRACT : The Adi Ganga is a palaeodistributary of the Bhagirathi, which was described as an important navigational channel in the mediaeval Bengali literature (*Mangalkavyas*). Its degenerated course is still traceable for 36 km downstream of Calcutta up to Surjyapur (22°18'N, 88°28'E) in the South 24-Parganas district, West Bengal. Beyond Surjyapur, at least eight different possibilities of its path and/or outfall positions (at Diamond Harbour, Kulpi, Gangasagar, Saptamukhi estuary and Hariyabhanga estuary) have been suggested by different authors. After critical evaluation of each of them, it can be fairly ascertained on the basis of the *Mangalkavyas*, satellite images and aerial photos, that the Adi Ganga continued for another 40 km up to the Gajmuri-Dighirpara region (22°01'N, 88°25'E). Downstream of that, its course is impossible to determine on the basis of any existing evidence but may have continued southwards following the behaviour of the major present-day estuaries.

Introduction

Sequential activation and abandonment of deltaic distributaries in the historical period is commonplace in most of the major world rivers. The principal course of the lower Bhagirathi-Hugli system in the western Ganga Brahmaputra delta (GBD) has similarly shown some important shifts during the last 400 years to which the rise and fall of a few major port-cities of the ancient and mediaeval Bengal were closely linked (Sherwill, 1858 ; Hunter, 1875, 1876 ; Wilson, 1895 ; Hirst 1916 ; Reaks, 1919 ; Mukerjee, 1938 ; Ray, 1947, 1949, 1979 ; R. C. Majumdar, 1971 ; Banerji, 1972; D. Majumdar, 1978 ; Rudra, 1986, 1987). During the 15th-17th century, the Bhagirathi used to get divided into three branches at the vicinity of Tribeni (*tribeni* = three branches of a river), about 175 km downstream of its off-take from the Ganga (Hunter, 1876 ; Wilson, 1895 ; Reaks, 1919). These were : (a) the Saraswati to the west, which used to drain into the sea through the present course of the Hugli downstream of Sankrail (Fig. 1) ; (b) the Bhagirathi-proper at the centre, which used to follow the present Hugli course upto Garden Reach (in south Calcutta) and then used to occupy the now-moribund channel of the Adi Ganga (*ādi* = old) and (c) the comparatively less significant Jamuna-Bidyadhari to the east. Both the Saraswati and Jamuna, like the Adi Ganga, have become almost completely inactive at present.

In this article, following a brief literature review, the position of the lower Adi Ganga, as suggested by different authorities, has been re-examined on the basis of circumstantial and direct evidences.

JOINS THE FOLLOWING MAP

JOINS THE PRECEDING MAP

Fig. 1 : The course of the Adi Ganga and its strandline localities. The outfall positions were suggested by (A) Hirst, 1916 (B) Mukerjee, 1938 and Mukherjee, 1976 (C) O'Malley, 1914 ; Dutt, 1934 ; Lahiri, 1936 and many others (D) Rudra, 1986. The present work supports and suggests (D) and (E).

Base map : Sol sheet no. 79B and 79C of 1943 edition. Many of the creeks and lakes shown here have since been decayed or reclaimed (cf. Fig. 3C). The Adi Ganga levee below Gariya is superposed from Landsat-5 TM FCC of 1986 (1:250,000).

Adi Ganga : a Palaeodistributary of the Bhagirathi

Location and Importance of the Upper Course

Holwell noted that 'a small brook' near Kalighat (now in south Calcutta : Fig. 1) was 'deemed to be the original course of the Ganges' by the local brahmins (Holwell, 1771). This

channel was shown to be draining into the Bidyadhari (upper Matla) below Baruipur in the 1778 *Bengal Atlas* of James Rennell (sheet no. 1). The initial written accounts of its moribund course, described in the early maps variously as the Govindapur Creek, Gunga *Nullah*, Surman's *Nala* (*nālā* = small channel) etc., were provided by the *Calcutta Review* (1852) and Sherwill (1858). Subsequently, Hunter (1875) identified it as the *Ādi Ganga* and observed how 'the Hindus still consider the route of the channel, sacred, and burn their dead on the sides of the tanks dug in its bed.' During 1775-77, a connection was made by Maj. William Tolly between the Hugli and Bidyadhari by means of a 27-km long canal which mostly followed the *Ādi Ganga* in its western section upto Gariya (Buckley, 1883). This canal, known as the Tolly's *Nala*, is still there but has lost its importance completely with the degeneration of the Bidyadhari (Fig. 1).

In the 1920-22 topographical maps (no. 79 B/7 and 79 B/8 ; of Survey of India (SoI), the course of the *Ādi Ganga* was shown in a completely decayed condition between Gariya and Surjyapur and then, as an active stretch, between the Chitraganja and Khari creeks, below Bishnupur. In the later 1:50,000 editions of these maps, resurveyed in 1959-60 and 1968-69 respectively, no trace of the palaeochannel between Gariya and Surjyapur was represented although the name *Ādi Ganga* was retained for the lower section of the still-active discontinuous stretch (Fig. 2).

The support for the observation that the *Ādi Ganga* constituted a major mediaeval outlet of the Bhagirathi mainly comes from the contemporaneous non-scale maps of the GBD prepared by Jao de Barros in 1552 and Van den Brouke in 1660 (see Mukerjee, 1938 for reproductions) where the channel was portrayed prominently. Some evidence can also be gathered from Bengali literature of the same period.

Shastri (1892) showed how the former course of the mediaeval Bhagirathi can clearly be traced by locating a number of old strandline villages mentioned in the *Manasār Bhāsān* (or *Manasāmangal*) – a latest 15th century Bengali verse composed by Bipradas Pipilai. Gradually, similar usefulness of some other literary works of the mediaeval Bengal also came into light. These included the *Chandimangal* of Kabikangkan Mukundaram Chakrabarti (Wilson, 1892 ; Bandyopadhyay, 1907 ; Reaks, 1919), the *Rāymangal* of Krishnaram Das (Bandyopadhyay, 1907; Dutt, 1935), the *Chaitanyabhāgabāt* of Brindaban Das (Dutt, 1929, 1935 ; Lahiri, 1936) and a few inferior and less important verses like the *Satyanārāyan Kathā* of Ayodhya Ram, the *Shitalāmangal* of Harideb and the *Kalu Rāyer Geet* of Dwija Nityananda (Basu, 1989). Works like these are now collectively referred to as the *Mangala* poems (Sen 1971) or *Mangalkāvya*s – a class of various cult-related narrative themes that flourished in the 13th-18th century Bengal (Bhattacharyya, 1975). Voyages to the ocean by their central characters, mostly merchants, was a theme common to a number of *Mangalkāvya*s. (The *Chaitanyabhāgabāt*, however, was an exception. Being a biography of the famous Vaishnavait saint Sri Chaitanyadeva, it described his journey, partly following the *Ādi Ganga*, to Puri, in the coastal Orissa.) Among these, the aforementioned works described the *Ādi Ganga* course of the Bhagirathi as a principal navigational channel to the Bay of Bengal. The strand-line localities of the then active river, cited in these poems, have been listed in Table-1 with some of their positions shown in Fig. 1. It may be noted

here that in a few of the earlier works (Reaks, 1919 ; Mukhopadhyay, 1921 ; Lahiri, 1936; Dutt, 1963 ; Mukherjee, 1983), some existing place-names were often arbitrarily ascribed to a *Mangalkāvya* although their mention cannot be found in the authentic versions of the same.

Table 1 : Strandline villages of the Adi Ganga palaeochannel and other relevant localities mentioned in the *Mangalkāvya*s

Author (with approximate date)	Title	Source	Relevant part of the work	Localities (arranged in downstream order according to descriptions) ¹
Bipradas Pipilai (latest 15th century – c.1496)	<i>Manasā-Bijay</i> or <i>Manasāmangal</i>	Sen (1958)	chapter-9, poem-6 ² chapter-10, poem-18	Dhalanda (in southwest Calcutta : Shastri, 1892), Kalighat, Churaghat (probably in south Calcutta : Shastri, 1892), <i>Dhanasthan</i> , Baruipur, Chhatrabhog, Hatiyagarh, Shatamukhi (hundred mouths of a river), sangam (confluence), dariya (sea)
Brindabandas (1535-36)	<i>Chaitanya-bhāgabat</i> or <i>Chaitanyamangal</i>	Sen (1991)	volume-3, chapter-2.	Atisara (in south Baruipur : Dutt, 1952) Chhatrabhog, Ambulinga (a Shiva image—now in Barashi), Shatamukhi
Mukundaram Chakrabarti (1594-1606)	<i>Chandimangal</i> (Dhanapati version)	Bhattacharyya (1966)	Three poems – <i>Magrā Abhimukhe Jātrā</i> , <i>Shrimanter Chhalane Debir Jukti</i> and <i>Bhāgirathir Tatabarnan</i>	Garifa, <i>Bajan</i> , Amalanga/ Amalangka (Ambulinga in Barashi) Chhatrabhog, Hatiyagarh, <i>Shilakut</i> , Magra
Krishnaram Das (1686)	<i>Rāymangal</i>	Bhattacharyya (1958)	poem-10	Dihi Medanmal, Hogla, <i>Patharghata</i> , Barasat, Khaniya
			poem-50	Kalyanpur, Malancha, Baruipur, Surjyapur, <i>Sadhughata</i> , Multi, <i>Hansuri</i> , Barasat, Barukshetra (Baharu), Jaynagar, Bishnupur, Ambulinga (in Barashi), Chhatrabhog, Gangadwara (Gangaduyara) <i>Tiyakhol</i> , Gajmuri, Kaddwip, <i>Betai</i> , <i>Dhamai</i> , <i>Gojana</i> , Magra.

1. Italicised place names could not be identified.

2. In all probability, the 4th poem of 9th chapter of this work, describing many settlements, is a later addition (Sen, 1958). Therefore, it has not been considered here.

Modern photo-interpretation based studies by Babu (1976) and Das et al. (1985) also detected that an approximately 5-km wide and 50-km long levee zone 'representing an ancient channel' extends from the south of Calcutta to the area around Khari which can closely be correlated with the course of the Adi Ganga (Fig. 1).

All these observations clearly indicate the importance of the Adi Ganga during the 15-17th century.

Reason of Decay

But why and when did the present course of the Bhagirathi-Hugli become established at the expense of the Adi Ganga? The *Calcutta Review* (1852) reported that 'the traveller never sees any funeral pyres smoking near the Hugli south of Calcutta, as the natives have a notion that this is a Khata Ganga (*khātā* = *kātā* = excavated), or a modern channel – only the ancient channel . . . is accounted sacred by them.' Reaks (1919) subsequently elaborated that, a connection between the former Bhagirathi, that used to flow through the Adi Ganga, and the lower Saraswati was 'at some period established by an artificial cut (from Garden Reach to Sankrail) . . . and the river appropriated and enlarged the channel, till it became the main stream, as a consequence of which both Tolly's Nullah (i.e. the Adi Ganga) and the upper Saraswati decayed' (Fig. 1). Recently, on the basis of thorough field investigations, Mukhopadhyay (1995) confirmed the absence of any crematorium or temple along this supposedly excavated stretch. Many authors (Ray, 1947, 1949 ; Bhattacharyya, 1954 ; Dutt, 1963 ; Basu, 1989 ; Dutta, 1992), presumably following prevailing legends, suggested that this artificial channel modification was probably executed during the times of Nawab Alivardi Khan, the ruler of Bengal between 1739 and 1756, to resuscitate the lower Saraswati and Rupnarayan. It probably involved in cutting and deepening of an already existing connection with help from Dutch engineers (Banerji, 1972). But, Basu (1992) has rightly expressed his doubts on the possibility of taking up of such a large scale project (the length of the supposedly excavated reach of the Hugli is about 10 km) at the middle of the 18th century – of which no proper record exists. He, like Ray (1902), attributed the event to natural processes.

The problem of Locating the Lower Course

Suggested Positions

Though there is an agreement on the 36-km upper course of the Adi Ganga (mainly due to its clearly defined physical existence), no general consensus on the position of its lower stretch, below Surjyapur, exists. The assumed courses of the channel downstream of Surjyapur and its outfall positions according to the different authors are as follows :

(i) *Sherwill (1858) and Reaks (1919)* : The Adi Ganga, in its lower course below Basantapur (south of Surjyapur), used to be 'broken into numerous mouths' – the principal ones being Baratala, Saptamukhi and Thakuran. The first among these reached the sea at Gangasagar, 'where all orthodox Hindoos agree that the Ganges mingles its waters with the ocean' (Sherwill, 1858). Reaks (1919) also agreed to this by stating that, before reaching the sea, the Adi Ganga used to 'split up into a number of branches one running into the lower Hugli at Diamond Harbour' (cf. Hirst, 1916).

(ii) *O'Malley, (1914, 1917), Dutt (1934, 1952, 1963) and Lahiri (1936)* : The Adi Ganga used to 'emerge out of Sundarbans' at Kakdwip on the Baratala and then used to follow the same river before turning west into Sagar island between Manasadwip and Dhablat areas (Fig. 1) and again turning south upto its confluence at Gangasagar (O'Malley, 1914, 1917). This view of O'Malley was also accepted by Mukerjee (1938). Subsequently, its course between Surjyapur and the Baratala was traced by Dutt (1934, 1952, 1963) and Lahiri (1936) as southwards through Baharu, Jaynagar, Barashi and Khari – beyond which existing tidal creeks like the Khari (E-W), Chora Gangagora (N-S), Gobadiya (N-S) and Ghibati (E-W) were used to be followed upto Kakdwip.

(iii) *Hirst (1916)* : The stream used to flow westwards from Surjyapur along the existing Surjyapur and Diamond Harbour tidal creeks to meet the Hugli at Diamond Harbour (Hirst, 1916 : P1, 7).

(iv) *SoI (1922-23, 1968-69)* : As mentioned earlier, in the two editions of SoI toposheet no. 79 C/8, a small 6.8 km north-south channel was shown as the Adi Ganga between Bishnupur and Sudhirghat in 1922-23 and between Mathurapur and Sudhirghat in 1968-69 (Fig. 1 and 2).

(v) *Lahiri (1936) and Mukherjee (1983)* : In 1920s, Kalidas Dutt prepared a map, not to scale, for the Varendra Research Society depicting the course of the Adi Ganga based on his and O'Malley's convictions outlined in (ii) (Dutt, 1934, 1952 : Maps). The information from this map was partly transferred on a large 1:253,440 sheet of 24-Parganas district by Lahiri (1936 : Map-4 : *Plan showing the course of the Adi Ganga river*). Based on this second map, Lahiri (1936) elaborated that the Sagar island stretch of the Adi Ganga, beyond Kakdwip, followed parts of the existing tidal creeks of Shikarpur, Chemaguri, Manchkhali (?Marichkhali), and Gangasagar (all N-S) and went through the present-day localities of Rudranagar, Bishnupur, Natendrapur, Narayaniabad, Magra and Gangasagar (Fig. 1). Later, in another map, Mukherjee (1983 : Fig. 4) showed this course as slightly offset from the present-day tidal channels all along. The basic path, however, was identical to that of Lahiri (1936). According to him, the suggested course was established on the basis of *Mangalkāvyas*, toposheets and field evidences which were not specified.

(vi) *Mukerjee (1938) and Mukherjee (1976)* : Although Mukerjee (1938), in the text of his work agreed to the suggestion of O'Malley (ii), in an accompanying map he showed the Adi Ganga as flowing southwards upto Khari, south of Chhatrabhog (the unequivocally identifiable southernmost strandline settlement mentioned in all the four *Mangalkāvyas*), and then taking a westward turn past Hatiyagarh to join Hugli (Mukerjee, 1938 : Fig. 7, not to scale). The well-known 1552 sketch map of Jao de Barros also showed Adi Ganga as flowing westwards a short distance after crossing Khari. Later, in a seemingly modified version of the above, the palaeochannel was shown by Mukherjee (1976 : Fig. 2) to approximately follow the existing railway track from near Bishnupur upto Laksmikantapur and then the Kulpi creek to join the Hugli near Kulpi.

(vii) *Bhattasali (1941) and Bagchi (1944)* : Based on the positions of the five outlets of the GBD compiled by Claudius Ptolemy in the 2nd century A.D., Bhattasali (1941) identified the

present Hariyabhanga confluence of the India-Bangladesh border as the 'Mega' estuary of Ptolemy. This, according to him, was the ancient outlet of the Adi Ganga. Later Bagchi (1944) accepted this view fully.

(viii) *Rudra (1986)* : From Khari onwards the river used to flow due south into the sea along the Gobadiya creek through the Saptamukhi estuary of today (Rudra, 1986 : Fig. III.8).

Evidence Cited for the Suggested Positions

Among the eight suggestions described above, only the ones suggested by O'Malley (1914, 1917), Dutt (1935, 1963), Lahiri (1936) and Rudra (1986), were supported by any clear argument. The arguments can be grouped in four classes of evidences.

Evidence from the Mangalkāvya : All the workers except O'Malley referred to a few or many of the *Mangalkāvya*-mentioned strandline settlements (Table-1). Among these, Dutt (1963) located Gangadhara, Hatiyagarh (the 10th Pargana of the 24-Parganas) and Magra along his proposed course of the Adi Ganga through Sagar. Lahiri (1936) argued that, among the four villages mentioned in the *Rāymangal* downstream of Khari – Kashinagar, Dhamai, Betai and Magra – the settlements of Dhamai and Betai cannot be identified with any of the present villages because, 'these two villages must have been in Sagar island but no trace can be found of their names now.' Rudra (1986), however, maintained that the Gobadiya-Saptamukhi course coincides most accurately with the descriptions made in the *Chaitanyabhāgabāt* and *Manasāmangal* in which the central character, Chando, supposedly performed some rituals at Gangasagar.

Evidence from Old Maps : Lahiri (1936) relied upon the maps of 49 *Patitabadi Taluks (Sheet-1)* by E. Princep (1822-25) and *Preliminary Map of the District 24-Parganas* by R. Smyth (c.1853) to locate some other place names incorporating the word 'Ganga' (e.g. Chara-Ganga, Chora Gangadora etc.), apart from Gangadhara. These, according to Lahiri (1936), add support to the proposed course past Khari.

Evidence from Local Legends and Rituals : O'Malley (1914) and Dutt (1963) were also impressed upon by the local legends, traditions and rituals such as burning of the dead at Gangadhara and Kakdwip along the proposed path below Khari. This, they thought, indicated the flow of the Adi Ganga through it.

Evidence from the Kapil Temple : Perhaps the most important piece of evidence of the Sagar island course of the Adi Ganga came from the location of the Kapil temple and the associated religious fair – one of the largest of its kind in India (Dutt, 1963). It is significant that this particular temple, a destination for the Hindu pilgrims through ages, is located near the minor Gangasagar creek at Gangasagar instead of a large estuary like the Hugli or Baratala, which are now directly connected with the Bhagirathi-Hugli. Moreover, although the temple had to be relocated at least four times between 1841 and present due to coastal erosion, it was never shifted from the Gangasagar confluence (Bandyopadhyay, 1994).

Discussion

The modern GBD includes some thirteen large estuaries along its coast – one at every 10 to 12 minutes of the longitude. Some of these obviously correlate with the five deltaic outlets described by Ptolemy in 150 B.C. ; but, it is inconceivable that they have not dissipated, formed or changed their positions during the last 2,000 years. It seems Bhattasali (1941), Bagchi (1944) and later Rudra (1981) placed unnecessary importance on the works of Ptolemy, who represented an age when maps were ‘largely the results of guesswork and hearsay’ (Gole, 1976).

It should be made clear at this point that the supposed course of the Adi Ganga could only traverse Sagar island, as many authors suggested, at a partially decayed state, because, it is physically impossible for any small sized island to continue on both sides of a major estuary of the GBD, that the lower Adi Ganga must had been. While the southern coast of the present Sagar island is just 11 km long, the width of any major estuary of this tide-dominated delta ranges from five to ten kilometres. Whether the Adi Ganga, which itself was a distributary, had a sub-distributary system (Sherwill, 1858, Reaks, 1919*i*), also cannot be ascertained because, the present distributaries of the Ganga hardly have any major subdistributary channel (e.g. the Hugli has only one, the Baratala, and that too branches off only 30 km upstream of the confluence), apart from the maze of minor inter-distributary tidal creeks.

As shown in Fig. 1, the *Mangalkāvya*-mentioned settlements like Multi, Gangaduyara, Hogla, Barasat, Baharu, Jaynagar, Khaniya, Bishnupur, Chhatrabhog, Ambulinga (Barashi) etc. form a 33-km linear pattern downstream of Surjyapur upto Gajmuri, west of Kashinagar. Although not shown in the SoI toposheets but clearly distinguished in aerial photomosaics (SoI, 1977 ; 1:50,000; 6 runs, 51 photos), a discontinuous palaeochannel (locally called *Gangār Bādā* upto Jaynagar), in form of many tanks and low-lying agricultural plots, exists all along these localities. Some of these tanks are associated with cremation grounds of high religious significance and their water is considered sacred. It is interesting to note that a similar site called Patalganga, near Krishnachandrapur, supposedly marks the place where the Ganga ceases to flow on the surface and enters into the *Pātala* – the nether world of Hindu mythology. Moreover, part of a very old pilgrim track (locally called *Dwārir Jāngāl* = *Dwari's* Path), connecting the religious spots of the region, is also traceable along the above mentioned settlements (Fig. 2).

Aerial photomosaics and suitably prepared satellite FCCs (e.g. in the 1986 Landsat-5 image used in Fig.1, TM bands 2, 3 and 4 were ascribed to blue, green, and red respectively) also clearly bring out the vegetated levees enclosing the Adi Ganga channel from south of the Calcutta Metropolitan District upto Bishnupur. Beyond Bishnupur, discontinuous levees follow the disposition of the above-mentioned course almost upto Dighirpara, seven kilometres south of Gajmuri.

Thus, the continuation of the Adi Ganga upto the Barashi-Khari region clearly rules out Hirst's suggestion (*iii*) and also proves the name ‘Adi Ganga’ used in the SoI toposheets to describe an active channel west of the *Mangalkāvya*-described course (*iv*) to be a misnomer. It actually is referred to by the local people as the ‘Mathurapur *Nala*’. Maps and images, however, fail to indicate the channel's lower course beyond Dighirpara.

Fig. 2 : Details of the localities along the lowermost identifiable course of the Adi Ganga. See text for further explanation. Base map : Sol sheet no. 79B/8 of 1968-69.

The whole of the region below the Chhatrabhog-Khari area was covered with dense mangrove jungle, called Sundarban, at the end of the mediaeval period. The *Mangalkāvya*-mentioned Hatiyagarh was one of Bengal's southern-most provinces that used to delimit the northern extension of Sundarban in the late 16th century (Blochmann, 1873). Systematic reclamation of these forests was initiated in 1770-73 by the British officials (Pargiter, 1934) and a project for clearing Sagar island, the favoured outfall locality of the Adi Ganga, was initiated in 1811 (Chapman, 1869). Although many authors suggested that parts of Sundarban was once populated (Bernier, c.1670 ; Rainey, 1868 ; Beveridge, 1876 ; Dutt, 1935 ; Haldar, 1983 ; Mukhopadhyay, 1995) and Princep (1831 in Carey, 1887) and the *Calcutta Review* (1859) did document the discoveries of ruined human habitations during reclamation of Sagar island, their names or identity remain obscured. So, linking the placenames described in the *Mangalkāvyas* with the villages and hamlets of the post-reclamation period seems quite inappropriate as the similarity must have been coincidental.

The name 'Magra' can be taken as a case in point. It has been mentioned in the works of Mukundaram Chakrabarti and Krishnaram Das (Table-1) and identified by Lahiri (1936), Dutt (1963) and Mukhopadhyay (1995) as the existing settlement of Magra Hat in the southern Sagar island (Fig. 1). While Das made a passing mention of 'durjay (invincible) Magra' in Rāymangal (Bhattacharyya, 1958), describing the place, Chakrabarti wrote :

- (a) *'Dure thāki Magrār jaler nihswan
Jena āshādiyā megher garjan
Mahanā bāhiyā sādhu kari twarā twarā
Prabesh karilā dingā durjay Magrā'*

– Bhattacharyya, 1966, p.319 ; repeated almost identically in p.220

(The distant sounds from the waters of Magra, resembled thundering storm clouds. The pious soul (i.e. the merchant Chando) hastily sailed through the mouth of the river and (his) boat entered the invincible Magra).

- (b) *'Pralayer brishti jena uthale Magrā '*
– ibid, p.220

(Magra swelled up like a cataclysmic deluge)

- (c) *Chāridike jal hailā dhabal
Magrā judiyā phenū'*

– ibid, p.223 ; repeated identically in p.321

(The water all around became white, Magra got covered with foams)

These extracts clearly establish Magra as a mouth of an estuary described in the midst of a storm, not a settlement. Haricharan Bandyopadhyay, the noted lexicographer of the Bengali language, also defined Magra simply as 'the mouth of the Ganga' (Bandyopadhyay, 1967). In J. Ellison's 1891 *Revenue Map of Sundarbans* (1:253,440) the locality of Magra Hat was shown to

be under *jungles*. The settlement first appeared in the 1:63,360 SoI toposheet of 1922-23 (No. 79 C/2).

It is evident from Table-1, there are at least ten villages, mentioned in the *Mangalkāvya*s, that cannot be correlated with any of the present-day settlements. Existence of more than one place with identical names (e.g. Kalyanpur, Magra Hat) further complicates the situation (Fig. 1). The described down-stream order of the villages also does not match with the reality in most cases. It is of course possible that a particular settlement was abandoned or renamed subsequent to its description. For example, Chhatrabhog, mentioned in all the four relevant *Mangalkāvya*s has now degenerated into such a small hamlet, that the large-scale SoI toposheet (79 B/8) of 1920-21 completely omitted its location while the subsequent 1968-69 edition referred to it, erroneously, as 'Chitrabhog'. However, discrepancies like these can also be explained by the fact that, with exception of the *Chaitanyabhāgabāt*, the *Mangalkāvya*s were, in essence, fictions – not geographical accounts.

As stated earlier, voyages in connection with maritime trade was a theme common to many of the *Mangalkāvya*s. But, it should be stressed that, there was a gap of at least hundred years between the time when Bengal was most actively involved in marine trading (Pal and Sen periods : 10th-12th century) and the period when the *Mangalkāvya*s were started to be written (Bhattacharyya, 1975). According to Sen (1945), the poets of the *Māngalkāvya*s mostly 'romanticised' a past tradition and, as Bhattacharyya (1975) noted, there are many proofs that these poets were poor in geographical knowledge. Thus, the possibility of erring in locating a given settlement or even imagining one always existed. Moreover, because the Bengali printing press started operation only from 1778, before the mid 19th century *Mangalkāvya* manuscripts (called *punthis*) were used to be hand copied for distribution. This greatly exaggerated the chances of interpolation, ranging from a word to a whole poem (Bhattacharyya, 1958 ; Sen, 1958; Choudhuri, 1987). This seems to be the only process how a settlement like Kakdwip could find its way into Das's 1686 *Rāymangal* although the area, comprising of Sundarban lot numbers 8 and 110, was granted for reclamation between 1830-31 and 1859 (Pargiter, 1934). Subtle to glaring differences in place names between different versions of a particular work also occurred in this way. The village 'Gangadhara' of the *Rāymangal*, widely quoted as an evidence for lower Adi Ganga's course by Lahiri (1936) and Dutt (1963), was actually a misrepresentation of 'Gangadwara' according to the most authentic edition of the work (Bhattacharyya, 1958). On the other hand, the place 'Kashinagar' quoted by Lahiri (1936), simply does not exist in the *Rāymangal* (Bhattacharyya, 1958).

In this connection, it may be pointed out that, according to the *Chaitanyabhāgabāt* itself, Sri Chaitanya, on his way to Puri, left for Orissa by boat from the landing place (*ghāt*) of Ambulinga (in Barashi) and thereafter took the land route across the Subarnarekha through Jaleswar and Jajpur (Sen, 1991). Obviously, the work could not have described any of the river mouths of the GBD. There is also no mention of Gangasagar in the Pipilai's *Manasāmangal* either. So, these two works cannot be used as evidences for the Adi Ganga's outlet position as Rudra (1986) attempted.

Fig. 3 : Changes in the configuration of Sagar island and location of Gangasagar – most commonly believed to be the outfall locality of the Adi Ganga. Scales are same for all the diagrams and placenames are as in the originals. *Source* : (A) Ritchie & Lackam's 'Chart of the Mouth of Hooghly River', 1:266,780 ; (B) Sol sheet no. 482-S.00, 1:253,440 ; (C) IRS-1B LISS-2 geocoded scene no. 79C01 & 79C02 (band-1, 5 Feb. 1996, 1:50,000 – all originally converted to 1:253,440.

In the Adi Ganga's course from Khari to Gangasagar, O'Malley (1914), Dutt (1934, 1963), Lahiri (1936) and others conceived a number of short stretches between successive right-angle bends. This orientation, however, is least possible for any major channel to adopt in a macrotidal estuarine situation. It probably would make more sense, hydrologically, to extend the Adi Ganga channel straight to south from the Gajmuri-Dighirpara area along the present-day Gobadiya-Saptamukhi (Rudra, 1986) or Moni-Thakuran as this would match with the behaviour of all the major presentday estuaries of the GBD. However, at the same time, it is perhaps meaningless to search for any geomorphic key to locate a palaeochannel hundreds, of years old in the rapidly changing channel and island configurations of an active delta. Let alone the mediaeval period, even in the late 18th century the configuration of Sagar island was very different from what it is now and it becomes mostly impossible to locate the outlet of the Gangasagar creek, the so called outlet of the Adi Ganga, in its present form (Fig. 3).

Any reliable information on the location of the transient Kapil temple (that has shifted at least four times in the last 150 years) about three to four hundred years ago is also unobtainable. Consequently, the suggested link between the Adi Ganga confluence and the Kapil temple so many years in the past can only be a conjecture rather than being a proof. What seems to be more plausible is that, the merchant ships of the mediaeval Bengal used to take a route through the smaller inner creeks of the Sundarban instead of the larger estuaries, which were obviously more open to the winds and waves as well as attacks from foreign pirate ships (Wilson, 1895). Gradually these routes became associated with legends and rituals, as the lower GBD was reclaimed and settled.

Conclusion

In view of all these observations, it can be surmised that while the course of the lower Adi Ganga, downstream of Surjyapur, can be established with some confidence up to Gajmuri-Dighirpara through Multi, Hogla, Jaynagar, Bishnupur, Chhatrabhog and Barashi, its position below that area can only be left undefined. It, however, seems more logical to extend the channel southwards from Gajmuri-Dighirpara either through the Saptamukhi estuary (Rudra, 1986) or through the Thakuran estuary than to route it through Sagar island, following the suggestions of O'Malley (1914), Dutt (1934, 1963), Lahiri (1936), Mukherjee (1983) and Mukhopadhyay (1995). The ideas of Hirst (1916), Mukerjee (1938), Bhattasali (1941) and Mukherjee (1976), that routed the Adi Ganga through some other areas, are similarly unacceptable.

Acknowledgements

I wish to thank Dr. S. P. Sinha Roy, Dr. P. B. Taran, Dr. A. Sarkar, Mr. S. Islam, Mr. A. Safi-Mandal, Prof. K. N. Mukherjee and Prof. M. K. Bandyopadhyay for their help and suggestions.

References

- Babu, P.V.L.P. (1976) : A review on the oil and gas prospects of the Bengal basin based on photogeomorphological studies, *Photonirvachak : J. Ind. Soc. Photointerpretation*, 4 (1-2) pp 1-3.
- Bagchi, K. (1944) : **The Ganges Delta**, Cal. Univ., Cal., pp 42-48.
- Bandyopadhyay, H. (1967) : **Dictionary of Bengali** (in Bengali), vol. 2, 2nd ed., Sahitya Akademi, N. Del., p 1706.
- Bandyopadhyay, P. (1314 BS/1907) : **Ancient History of Bengal** (in Bengali, pt. 1, Pub. by P.B. Banerji, Cal., pp 16-19.
- Bandyopadhyay, S. (1994) : *Sagar Island : Evolution, Landforms and Environmental Management*, unpublished Ph.D. thesis, (Geogr. Dept.) Cal. Univ., Cal., 122 p.
- Banerji, A.K. (1972) : **West Bengal District Gazetteers : Hooghly**, Govt. of West Bengal, pp 23-26.
- Basu, A.K. (1989) : **History of the Course of the Ganga** (in Bengali), West Bengal State Book Board, pp 107-117.
- Basu, A.K. (1992) : **Ecological and Resource Study of the Ganga Delta (in India)**, K.P. Bagchi and Co., Cal., p 14.
- Bernier, F. (c.1670) : **Travels in the Mogul Empire**, Tr. Brock. I. (1826), Ed. Constable, A. (1891), 1968 reprint, S. Chand and Co., N. Del., pp 175, 442-443.
- Beveridge, H. (1876) : Were the Sundarbans inhabited for in ancient times ? *J. Asia. Soc. Bengal*, 45(1), pp 71-76.
- Bhattacharyya, A. (1975) : **History of the Bengali Mangalkāvya**s (in Bengali), 6th ed., A Mukherji and Co. Pvt. Ltd., Cal., pp (20), 11-14, 61-64, 127-130, 467.
- Bhattacharyya, B. (Ed : 1966) : **Kabikangkan Mukundaram Chakrabarti's Chandimangal : The Story of Dhanapati** (in Bengali), Cal. Univ., Cal., pp 1-2, 219-223, 317-322, 482-483.
- Bhattacharyya, K. (1954) : **Rivers of Bengal and Planning** (in Bengali), Bidyodaya Libr. Ltd., Cal., pp 31-48.
- Bhattacharyya, S. (Ed : 1958) : **The Works of Poet Krishnaram Das**, Cal. Univ., Cal., pp 179-181, 242-244.
- Bhattachali, N.K. (1941) : Antiquity of the lower Ganges and its courses, *Sci. and Cult.*, 7(5), pp 233-239.
- Blockmann, H. (1873) : Contributions to the Geography and History of the Bengal (Mohammedan Period), *J. Asia. Soc. Bengal*, 1(3), 1968 reprint, Asia. Soc., Cal., pp 9, 19-20.
- Buckley, R.B. (1883) : A brief history of the Calcutta and its eastern canals, in : **Selections from the Records of the Bengal Government Containing Papers from 1865 to 1904**, Bengal Secretariat Press, Cal., pp 156-168.
- (*The Calcutta Review* (1852) : Calcutta in olden times – its localities, 18, pp 275-320.
- (*The Calcutta Review* (1859) : The Gangetic Delta, 32, pp 1-25.
- Chapman, R.B. (1869) : Official paper no. 103CE (dated 28th Dec., 1867), in : **Correspondence Relating to the Settlement of Saugor Island for 1867**, Bengal Secretariat Book Depot., Cal., pp 1-19.
- Choudhuri, A.M. (1987) : The Geographical identity of Bengal (in Bengali), in : Anisujaman (Ed) : **History of Bengali Literature**, vol. 1, Bangla Akademi, Dhaka, pp 1-48.
- Das, D. K., Majumdar, I.P. and Ganguly, A. (1985) : Evolution of the landscapes in the Calcutta Sundarban coastal area of South Bengal, India, *Pr. Ind. Acad. Sci. (Earth Planet. Sci)*, 95(3), pp 143-152.

- Dutt, K. (1929) ; The antiquities of Khari, Appendices to the *Ann. Rep. of Varendra Res. Soc.* (Monograph-3), pp 4-13.
- Dutt, K. (1341 BS/1934) : Poundrabardhan and Barddhamanbhukti (in Bengali), article read in 1st Annual Conf., Bangiya Sahitya Parishad, reprinted in : Dutt, K. (1989) : **The Past of South 24-Parganas** (in Bengali), vol. 2, Sundarban Regional Museum, Baruipur, pp 87-91.
- Dutt, K. (1935) : A brief historical account of Sundarban (in Bengali), in : Sen, D.C. : **The Greater Bengal** (in Bengali), vol. 2, Cal. Univ., Cal., pp 1126-1132.
- Dutt, K. (1359 BS/1952) : Chhatrabhog (in Bengali), *Prabasi*, 52(2), pp 433-438.
- Dutt, K. (1963) : History of the Adi Ganga (in Bengali), *Somprakash Sahityapatra*. Reprinted in : Dutt, K. (1989) : **The Past of South 24-Parganas** (in Bengali), vol. 1, Sundarban Regional Museum, Baruipur, pp 54-63.
- Dutta, S. (1992) : From Tamralipti to Kidderpore dock : a historic voyage in time ; *Marine Wing News Letter, Geol. Surv. Ind.*, 8(2), pp 7-11.
- Gole, S. (1976) : **Early maps of India**, Sanskriti/Arnold Heinemann Pub., N. Del., p 11.
- Haldar, N. (1983) : Archaeological treasures of Diamond Harbour sub-division (in Bengali). in **24 Parganas Archaeological Conference**, Baruipur, pp 55-57.
- Hirst, F.C. (1916) : **Report on the Nadia Rivers 1915**, Bengal Secretariat Book Depot, Cal., Plate-7.
- Holwell, J. Z. (1771) : **Interesting Historical Events, Relative to the Provinces of Bengal and the Empire of Indostan**, pt. 3, T. Becket and P.A. De Hondt., Lond., pp 130-131.
- Hunter, W.W. (1875) : **A Statistical Account of Bengal**, vol. 1, Trübner and Co., Lond., p 29.
- Hunter, W.W. (1876) : **A Statistical Account of Bengal**, vol. 3, Trübner and Co., Lond., p 262.
- Lahiri, A.C. (1936) : **Final Report on the Survey and Settlement Operations in the District of 24 Parganas for the Period 1924-1933**, Bengal Govt. Press, Cal., pp 14-15, Map-4.
- Majumdar, D. (1978) : **West Bengal District Gazetteers : Nadia**, Govt. of West Bengal, pp 6-8.
- Majumdar, R.C. (1971) : **History of Ancient Bengal**, G. Bharadwaj and Co., Cal., pp 2-3.
- Mukerjee, R.K. (1938) : **The Changing Face of Bengal : a Study of Riverine Economy**, Cal. Univ., Cal., pp 166-168, plate-2.6.
- Mukherjee, K.N. (1976) : Sociological inter-action on changing landuse patterns (case studies in the southern 24-Parganas district), *Geogr. Rev. Ind.*, 38(2), pp 109-122.
- Mukherjee, K.N. (1983) : History of Settlement in the Sundarban of West Bengal, *Ind. J. Landscape Systems*, 6(1-2), pp 1-19.
- Mukhopadhyay, H. (1921) : **Calcutta of Past and Present** (in Bengali), 2nd ed., 1991 reprint (Ed. Ray, N.R.), K.P. Bagchi and Co. Pvt. Ltd., Cal., pp 15, 182-183, 185.
- Mukhopadhyay, N. (1995) : **An Archeological Traverse along the Adi Ganga** (in Bengali), Vostok, Cal., 112p.
- O'Malley, L.S.S. (1914) : **Bengal District Gazetteers : 24-Parganas**, Bengal Secretariat Book Depot, Cal., pp 7-8.
- O'Malley, L.S.S. (1917) : **Bengal Bihar Orissa and Sikkim**, Cambr. Univ. Press, Lond., p 45.
- Pargiter, F.E. (1934) : **A Revenue History of Sundarbans, 1765-1870**, Bengal Govt. Press, Alipur, pp 1-2.
- Princep. G.A. (1831) : **Sketch of the Proceedings and Present Position of the Saugor Island Society and its Lesees**. Extracted in : Carey, W.H. (1887) : **The Good Old Days of Honourable John Company etc.**, 1907 reprint, vol. 2, R. Cambay and Co., Cal., pp 122-125.

- Rainey, H.G. (1868) : What was the Sundarban originally, and when, and wherefore did it assume its existing state of utter desolation ? (abstr. w. discussion), *Proc. Asia. Soc. Bengal : Jan.-Dec. 1868*, pp 264-273.
- Ray, A.K. (1902) : A Short History of Calcutta, in : **Census of India 1901**, vol. 7, pt. 1, Bengal Secretariat Press, Cal. p 13.
- Ray, N.R. (1354 BS/1947) : **Rivers of Bengal** (in Bengali), Vishva Bharati, Cal., pp 15-16.
- Ray, N.R. (1356 BS/1949) : **History of the Bengalees : Early Part** (in Bengali), Book Emporium, Cal., pp 93-94, 105.
- Ray, N.R. (1979) : Tamralipta and Gange : two port-cities of ancient Bengal and connected consideration, *Geogr. Rev. Ind.*, 43(3), pp 205-222.
- Reaks, H.G. (1919) : Report on the physical and hydraulic characteristics of the delta, in : Stevenson Moore et al. (nine authors) : **Report on the Hooghly River and its Headwaters**, vol. 1, apndx. 2, Bengal Secretariat Book Depot, Cal., pp 29-132.
- Rudra, K. (1981) : Identification of the ancient mouths of the Ganga as described by Ptolemy, *Geogr. Rev. Ind.*, 40(2), pp 97-104.
- Rudra K. (1986) : *The History of Development of the Bhagirathi Hooghly River System and Some Connected Consideration*, unpublished Ph. D. thesis, (Geogr. Dept.) Cal. Univ., Cal., 137p.
- Rudra, K. (1987) : Quaternary history of the lower Ganga distributaries, *Geogr. Rev. Ind.*, 49(3), pp 38-48.
- Sen, S. (1352 BS/1945) : **The Bengal and the Bengalees of the Mediaeval Age** (in Bengali), Vishva Bharati, Cal., p 46.
- Sen, S. (Ed : 1958) : **Vipradasa's Manasā-Vijaya** (in Bengali with English translation), Asia. Soc., Cal., pp iv-v, 143-146, 273-275.
- Sen, S. (1971) : **History of Bengali Literature**, 2nd ed., Sahitya Akademi, N. Del., pp 52, 60.
- Sen, S. (Ed : 1991) : **Brindabandas's Chaitanyabhāgabat** (in Bengali), 2nd printing, Sahitya Akademi, N. Del., pp 246-258.
- Shastri, H. (1892) : Notes on the banks of the Hugli in 1495, *Proc. Asia. Soc. Bengal : Jan.-Dec., 1892*, pp 193-197.
- Sherwill, W.S., (1858) : Report on the Rivers of Bengal, in : **Selections from the Records of the Bengal Govt.**, vol. 29, G.A. Savielle Printing and Pub. Co. (Ltd.), Cal., pp 1-18.
- Wilson, C.R. (1892) : Note on the topography of the river in the 16th century from Hugli to the sea as represented in the Da Asia of De Barros, *J. Asia, Soc. Bengal*, 61(1), pp 109-117.
- Wilson, C.R. (1895) : **Early Annals of the English in Bengal**, vol. 1, reprinted in : Wilson, C.R. and Carey, W.H. (1968, Ed. Mookerji, A.) : **Glimpses of Olden Times, India under East India Company**, Eastlight Book House, Cal., pp 88-100.